

1 **Evolution of near-term atmospheric methane and associated temperature response**
2 **under the Global Methane Pledge: insights from an Earth system model**

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19 **Key Points:**

- 20 • Current Global Methane Pledge cuts only 10% of anthropogenic emissions by 2030, far
21 below the 30% target.
- 22 • Maximum technically feasible reductions are needed to meet climate goals.
- 23 • Arctic gains most, with up to 2 {degree sign}C less warming under stronger methane
24 cuts.
- 25

26 **Abstract**

27 Methane is a powerful greenhouse gas with a shorter lifetime than carbon dioxide (CO₂),
28 making it an important target for near-term climate action. The Global Methane Pledge (GMP)
29 aims to cut anthropogenic methane emissions by 30% from 2020 levels by 2030. Using an Earth
30 system model with interactive CH₄ sources and sinks, we assess the Pledge's impact through
31 2050. Results show that current GMP commitments deliver only a 10% cut by 2030—well below
32 the target. Only the maximum technically feasible reduction (MTFR) pathway can achieve the
33 30% goal. By 2050, current GMP commitments lowers methane concentrations by 3% relative
34 to 2025, while MTFR achieves 8%. Both pathways slow warming slightly, avoiding about 0.1 °C
35 of global temperature rise, with the Arctic seeing the greatest benefits (up to 2 °C less
36 warming). Without wider participation, the GMP with current signatories will fall short of its
37 targets and Paris Agreement goals.

38 **Plain Language Summary**

39 Methane (CH₄) is a powerful greenhouse gas that warms the planet more strongly than carbon
40 dioxide (CO₂) but lasts for a shorter time in the atmosphere. Because of this, cutting methane
41 emissions can deliver fast climate benefits. The Global Methane Pledge (GMP) was launched to
42 cut human-caused methane emissions by 30% from 2020 levels by 2030. This study used a
43 climate model to test whether the GMP can reach its target. Results show that today's GMP
44 commitments would only achieve a 10% cut by 2030—well short of the goal. By 2050, GMP leads
45 to a 3% drop in methane concentrations, avoiding about 0.1 °C of global temperature rise, with

46 the Arctic gaining the most benefit. However, without more countries joining in-especially the
47 largest emitters-the GMP may not meet its goals or align with Paris Agreement climate limits.

48 **1 Introduction**

49 Methane (CH₄) is a powerful greenhouse gas with a global warming potential about 28
50 times that of carbon dioxide (CO₂) over a 100-year timeframe (IPCC, 2023), and a relatively
51 short atmospheric lifetime of roughly a decade (IPCC, 2023). CH₄ currently contributes a
52 disproportionate share of anthropogenic warming (~25–30%) (UNEP & CCAC, 2023). IPCC's
53 Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) finds that strong, rapid and sustained methane mitigation would
54 significantly limit near-term global warming and improve air quality by reducing tropospheric
55 ozone formation (IPCC, 2023), yielding climate benefits much more quickly than CO₂ reductions,
56 and helping keep the Paris Agreement's 1.5 °C target. UNEP's Global Methane Assessment
57 found that a 45% reduction in human-caused CH₄ emissions by 2030 could avert nearly 0.3 °C of
58 global warming by the 2040s (UNEP & CCAC, 2023). Even the more modest goal of the Global
59 Methane Pledge – a 30% cut in CH₄ emissions by 2030 – would avoid at least ~0.2 °C of warming
60 by 2050 (UNEP, 2021).

61 The Global Methane Pledge (GMP) is an international initiative to operationalize these
62 science-based insights into policy action. Launched at the 26th Conference of the Parties
63 (COP26) in 2021, the GMP is non-binding and without country-specific quotas, and now has
64 over 158 signatory countries collectively aiming to cut global CH₄ emissions by at least 30%
65 below 2020 levels by 2030 (UNEP, 2021). However, some large emitting countries, including
66 China, India, Russia, and South Africa, responsible for much of the remaining 45% of global CH₄

67 emissions are currently not signatories. Participants agreed to develop national Methane Action
68 Plans (MAPs) or roadmaps outlining mitigation policies across major CH₄-emitting sectors
69 (energy, agriculture, and waste). As of April 2024, 12 countries (Brazil, Canada, China, Finland,
70 Iceland, Netherlands, Norway, Republic of Korea, United Kingdom, USA, and Vietnam) plus the
71 European Union had submitted detailed Methane Action Plans (MAP) to the Climate and Clean
72 Air Coalition (UNEP & CCAC, 2024). Analyses suggest that fully implementing the MAPs already
73 identified in Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) to their maximum technical potential
74 could achieve roughly a 30% global reduction, meeting the GMP goal. Available technologies
75 could eliminate a large fraction of CH₄ emissions cost-effectively (e.g., up to 75% of methane
76 from oil and gas operations can be abated with existing methods, roughly half at no net cost)
77 (UNEP, 2021). Recent research showed that CH₄ reductions could reduce climate-related
78 damages in 2050 by more than a trillion dollars a year while costing only one sixth of the
79 damages they would avoid (Stoerk et al., 2025).

80 Earth system models (ESM) are principal tools to assess the impacts of climate
81 mitigation on the global and regional scale. In most cases, ESMs use prescribed atmospheric
82 CH₄ concentration pathways; however, it is important to account for sources and sinks of CH₄
83 when assessing its impacts and future evolution (Shindell et al., 2024). Of all the ESMs that
84 contributed to the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6: Eyring et al., 2016),
85 only one – the NASA Goddard Institute for Space Studies (GISS) chemistry–climate model
86 version E2.1 (GISS-E2-1-G: Kelley et al., 2020; Im et al., 2025a) - used interactive CH₄ emissions
87 and chemistry. Since CMIP6, more ESMs have developed interactive CH₄ sources, including UK-
88 ESM1 (Folberth et al., 2022), and EMAC (Stecher et al., 2025).

89 To date, very few studies assessed the impacts of the Pledge. Cael and Goodwin (2023)
90 used an emulator to quantify the difference in global annual mean surface temperature of the
91 GMP versus the equivalent amount of CO₂ emission reduction and found that the GMP initially
92 results in greater relative cooling than the avoidance of the equivalent amount of CO₂
93 emissions over the same period. Predybaylo et al. (2025) used the EMAC model with interactive
94 CH₄ emissions and found that reducing CH₄ emissions decelerates global warming through
95 changes in radiative fluxes and shortening the lifetime of tropospheric CH₄ and other gases, as
96 well as leading to air quality improvement from a reduction of surface ozone. These studies
97 assumed a specific percentage of global reduction in CH₄ emissions. To our knowledge, our
98 study is the first study that uses an ESM (GISS-E2.1-G) with interactive CH₄ sources to evaluate
99 the impacts of the Pledge and the MAPs, using realistic emission projections based on the
100 current status of the participation in the Pledge and/or MAPs.

101 **2 Materials and Methods**

102 We used the GISS-E2.1-G ESM (Kelley et al., 2020), with a horizontal resolution of 2°
103 latitude by 2.5° longitude and 40 vertical layers extending from the surface to 0.1 hPa in the
104 lower mesosphere. GISS-E2.1-G includes inorganic tropospheric chemistry of Ox, NOx, HOx, CO,
105 and organic chemistry of CH₄ (Shindell et al., 2013) and higher hydrocarbons using the CBM-IV
106 scheme (Gerry et al., 1989). CH₄ is only removed by oxidation via the hydroxyl radical (OH) and
107 the soil sink. Other important chemical CH₄ sinks such as chlorine (Basu et al., 2022) are not

108 included in the GISS-E2.1-G as tropospheric halogens are not part of the model (Im et al.,
109 2025a).

110 CH₄ emissions from wetlands in GISS-E2.1-G are calculated online using upper layer soil
111 temperature and precipitation anomalies (Shindell et al., 2003; 2004), with prescribed wetland
112 locations and is lumped with CH₄ emissions from tundra (Shindell et al., 2013), which are then
113 modified by the emissions model (Shindell et al., 2003). In addition, in the present study, the
114 wetland emissions, which are very uncertain and comprise the largest contribution among the
115 natural emissions (Saunois et al., 2025), have been tuned by a factor calculated to get a similar
116 burden and lifetime as in the prescribed simulations (Im et al., 2011; 2025a) during the
117 historical period (1995-2023) in order to better follow the global observations (Saunois et al.,
118 2020). This tuning approach does not consider the changes in OH or regional differences in CH₄
119 emissions and concentrations but improves the model performance by getting closer to the
120 observed global CH₄ concentrations. The calculated wetland tuning factor for the 1995-2014
121 period is then applied also in the future period 2015-2050.

122 We used anthropogenic emissions from IIASA's GAINS model version 2.1 (Klimont et al.,
123 2025). These are recent updates of emission scenarios for CH₄ described in more detail by
124 Höglund-Isaksson et al. (Höglund-Isaksson et al., 2012; 2020; 2023) and for air pollutants (IIASA
125 ECLIPSE scenarios) described in Stohl et al. (2015), and in our Supplementary materials.
126 Methods and assumptions for bottom-up estimation of sector-level CH₄ emissions in GAINS are
127 documented in the Supplementary materials of Höglund-Isaksson (2012; 2017), Höglund-
128 Isaksson et al. (2020; 2023), and Gomez-Sanabria et al. (2022). A comparison of global

129 anthropogenic CH₄ emissions in year 2020 across recent studies (Figure S1) shows that the
130 GAINS estimate of 350 Tg yr⁻¹ falls well within the range of 325 to 364 Tg yr⁻¹ of other
131 independently produced bottom-up (BU) inventories, i.e., EDGAR (Crippa et al., 2024), CEDS
132 (Hoesly et al., 2024) and USEPA (2019; 2025). The Global Carbon Project (Saunois et al., 2024)
133 presents global anthropogenic CH₄ emissions in year 2020 ranging between 345 and 409 Tg yr⁻¹
134 across referenced BU inventories and between 368 and 409 across top-down (TD) inverse
135 model results. While EDGAR, CEDS, and USEPA (2025) estimate lower anthropogenic emissions
136 of fossil origin than the TD range of 101 to 133 Tg yr⁻¹, GAINS and USEPA (2019) fall within the
137 TD range.

138 The Current Legislation (CLE) scenario (2015-2050) assumes efficient implementation of
139 current CH₄, and air pollution legislation enacted before 2018. The Maximum Technical Feasible
140 Reduction (MTFR) scenario assumes full implementation of best available emission reduction
141 technologies and practices. Further details on assumptions for the CLE and MTFR scenarios for
142 CH₄ can be found in Höglund-Isaksson et al. (2020). In addition, three intermediate scenarios
143 were developed for this study reflecting different levels of compliance with adopted CH₄ policy
144 frameworks. The GMP scenario reflects future emissions when all GMP signatories jointly
145 follow through on the Pledge, thus reducing their anthropogenic CH₄ emissions by 30%, and
146 non-signatory countries continue along the CLE scenario trajectory. The MAP scenario is a
147 model interpretation of the impact on future CH₄ emissions from full implementation of the
148 measures mentioned in the MAPs, and assuming all countries having not submitted a MAP
149 continue along the CLE scenario trajectory. The Full Policy scenario (POL) combines the GMP

150 and MAP scenarios, i.e., GMP signatory countries meet the pledged target and all measures
 151 mentioned in the MAPs are fully implemented.

152 We carried out five sets of fully-coupled simulations (Table 1), each consisting of three
 153 ensemble members, and initialized from fully coupled recent past simulations to ensure a
 154 smooth continuation from recent past to future. GMP, MAP, and POL scenarios only perturb
 155 anthropogenic CH₄, while the MTFR scenario also reduces other short-lived climate pollutants
 156 (SLCP) along with CH₄. Other greenhouse gases than CH₄, i.e. CO₂ and N₂O, are prescribed using
 157 global annual mean concentrations used in CMIP6. All simulations have been performed at the
 158 LUMI supercomputer (<https://lumi-supercomputer.eu/>). One simulation year takes 6.33 hours,
 159 giving 6.6 days simulation time for one ensemble member for the recent past simulation, 9.5
 160 days for one CLE simulation, 6.9 years for GMP, MAP, and POL simulations each, and 5.5 days
 161 for an MTFR simulation.

162 **Table 1.** Emission scenarios used in the present study

Scenarios	Period	Perturbed Emissions
Recent past (CLE)	1990-2014	No perturbation - Historical baseline
CLE	2015-2050	No perturbation - 2015-2050 baseline
GMP	2025-2050	Anthropogenic + biomass burning CH ₄
MAP	2025-2050	Anthropogenic + biomass burning CH ₄
POL	2025-2050	Anthropogenic + biomass burning CH ₄
MTFR	2030-2050	Anthropogenic + biomass burning CH ₄ + other SLCPs

163

164 **3 Results**

165 Anthropogenic CH₄ emissions continue to increase in the baseline (CLE) scenario, while
166 the Methane Action Plan (MAP) scenario initially leads to a small emission reduction, but then
167 continues to increase (Figure 1a). The (current status) GMP scenario leads to a reduction of 10%
168 by 2030 in global anthropogenic CH₄ emissions, to 314 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹, however, does not reach the
169 GMP target level of 30% below the 2020 level (245 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹). The POL scenario, which is the
170 combination of GMP and MAP leads to a slightly larger reduction (to 307 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹) than GMP
171 alone but still cannot achieve the GMP target value. Only the MTRF scenario can fulfil the
172 Pledge's emission reduction objective, leading to a reduction to 242 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹. Therefore, the
173 MTRF scenario corresponds, approximately, to full fulfilment of the Pledge, also in agreement
174 with the 30% reduction scenarios implemented in Predybaylo et al. (2025).

175 As wetland CH₄ emissions continue to increase slightly in all simulations (Figure 1b), the
176 total emissions (Figure 1c) follow a very similar trend to that of the anthropogenic emissions.
177 The natural annual CH₄ emissions (320±5 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹) averaged over the 2000-2015 period,
178 dominated by the wetland CH₄ emissions (272±5 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹) are comparable to the
179 anthropogenic CH₄ emissions (323±11 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹) (Figure 1d). Depending on the level of
180 reduction of the anthropogenic emissions under different scenarios, this balance between the
181 anthropogenic and natural emissions either shifts towards more anthropogenic emissions
182 under CLE and MAP, or towards natural sources under GMP, POL, and MTRF, where larger
183 anthropogenic emission reductions take place (Figure S2). Our 272 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹ wetland CH₄
184 emissions are higher than the estimate of 155-217 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹ (Saunois et al., 2020). On the
185 other hand, the global anthropogenic CH₄ emission in the present study (323 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹) is

186 slightly lower than a recent estimate of 369 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹ (Saunois et al., 2025). Other natural
 187 methane sources in our study are fixed at values of 20 Tg yr⁻¹ for termites, close to the 25 Tg
 188 CH₄ yr⁻¹ by Saunois et al. (2025). The combined geological + ocean + lake sources are fixed to
 189 and 27 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹ taken from Fung et al. (1991). These are likely on the low side compared to
 190 recent literature, where global oceanic CH₄ emissions are estimated to be 6-12 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹
 191 (Weber et al., 2019) and lake emissions are estimated to be 24.0±8.4 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹ (Zhuang et al.,
 192 2023).

193

194

195 **Figure 1.** Global anthropogenic (a), wetland (b) and total (c) CH₄ emissions in the 2010-2050
 196 period, and the 2000-2015 mean break down of global CH₄ emissions in anthropogenic,
 197 biomass burning, natural (wetlands and tundra, termites, ocean), with yellow bars indicating
 198 standard deviation (d).

199 The global CH₄ concentrations simulated under the different emission scenarios are
200 presented in Figure 2a, along with the global and annual mean observations during the 2010-
201 2024 period from NOAA (Lan et al., 2025). The simulated global CH₄ concentrations agree well
202 with the observations, with a Pearson correlation (*r*) of 0.99 and a normalized mean bias (*NMB*)
203 of -3%. The global CH₄ concentrations continue to increase in the CLE and MAP scenarios from
204 1.88±0.01 ppm in 2025 to 2.13±0.001 ppm (13%) under CLE and 2.07±0.001 ppm (10%) under
205 MAP in 2050. The (current) GMP scenario leads to a decrease in global CH₄ concentrations from
206 1.88±0.01 ppm in 2025 to 1.82±0.003 ppm (-3%) in 2050, while the POL scenario leads to a
207 slightly larger decrease, to 1.79±0.01 ppm (-5%). The largest reduction is simulated for the
208 MTRF scenario, which leads to a decrease from 1.92±0.01 ppm in 2030 to 1.77±0.01 ppm (8%)
209 in 2050 (a reduction of 6% compared to 2025). These responses to emission changes are lower
210 than in Predybaylo et al. (2025) and Allen et al. (2021). However these studies assumed a full
211 compliance to a global 30% and 40% CH₄ emission reduction while our study only considers the
212 current signatories to the Pledge, which is much smaller than a full compliance (Figure 1a).

213 The global CH₄ lifetime (Figure 2b) is estimated to be around 8-8.5 years in all scenarios,
214 except for the MTRF, which increases the lifetime to more than 9 years. Although the lifetime
215 substantially increases in the MTRF scenario, the decrease in global average concentration is
216 greatest under this scenario, which means that the model is driven by the large reduction in the
217 emissions (Figure 1a,b). The GMP and the POL scenarios lead to a slight decrease in the lifetime
218 of CH₄, from 8.4 years in 2025 to 8.1 years by 2050, while the MAP scenario follows the CLE
219 scenario.

220 The top-of-the-atmosphere (TOA) CH₄ radiative forcing (RF_{CH₄}) has been calculated
 221 based on Etminan et al. (2016) and is shown in Figure 2c. It should be noted that all scenarios
 222 except for MTRF quantify the direct radiative forcing from CH₄-only changes, while for MTRF,
 223 the estimated forcing is due to a combination of changes in CH₄ and other SLCF emissions.
 224 Under CLE, RF_{CH₄} continues to increase from 0.53±0.01 Wm⁻² in 2010 to 0.59±0.01 Wm⁻² in
 225 2025, then to 0.69±0.01 Wm⁻² under CLE and to 0.68±0.02 Wm⁻² under the MAP scenario in
 226 2050. Under the GMP and POL scenarios RF_{CH₄} decreases from 0.59±0.01 Wm⁻² in 2025 to
 227 0.56±0.02 Wm⁻² and 0.54±0.04 Wm⁻² in 2050, respectively. The largest reduction is calculated
 228 under the MTRF scenario, which reduces the RF_{CH₄} to 0.61±0.01 Wm⁻² in 2030 and to 0.53±0.03
 229 Wm⁻² in 2050, bringing the forcing back to 2010 levels.

241 **Figure 2.** Annual mean global mean CH₄ concentrations (a), lifetime (b), TOA radiative forcing
242 (c) and surface temperature (d) in the different simulations. Black dots in (a) and (d) show
243 global and annual mean observations from NOAA and ERA5, respectively.

244

245 The geographical distribution of the concentration response to the different emission
246 scenarios, averaged over the 2046-2050 period, relative to the CLE scenario are shown in Figure
247 S3. Smallest concentration reductions take place in remote areas, over the southern
248 hemisphere and over the Southern Ocean. Largest reductions take place over land, especially
249 where the emission regions are located such as in North America and Europe. Particularly large
250 reductions are simulated over the Persian Gulf region in the GMP and thus POL scenarios.
251 Southeast Asia, which is one of the largest emitting regions, lacks signatories to the GMP; some
252 countries in the region have, however, submitted MAPs. Therefore, the model predicts a large
253 response over Southeast Asia under the MAP and POL scenarios, as well as under the MTFR
254 scenario.

255 The surface temperature response to the changes in CH₄ emissions are shown in Figure
256 2d. The model results are in good agreement with the ERA5 observations (Hersbach et al.,
257 2020) for the 2010-2024 period, with a r of 0.77 and a NMB of +4%. Under all scenarios, surface
258 temperatures continue to increase, in agreement with earlier studies (e.g. Predybaylo et al.,
259 2025), from 15.1 ± 0.19 °C in 2010 to 16.2 ± 0.10 °C in 2050. In order to evaluate the extent to
260 which global surface temperatures respond to the different emission scenarios, we compared
261 the 2046-2050 mean global surface temperature from the CLE scenario with that of the GMP,
262 MAP, POL and MTFR scenarios. The GMP scenario avoids 0.11 ± 0.11 °C warming compared to

263 the CLE scenario, while the MAP and POL scenarios avoid 0.07 ± 0.16 °C and 0.09 ± 0.15 °C,
264 respectively. The MTRF scenario avoids 0.13 ± 0.12 °C warming compared to the CLE scenario.
265 These estimates are lower and have greater associated uncertainties than those in a previous
266 study by Cael and Goodwin (2023), which estimated 0.21 ± 0.06 °C lower global warming under a
267 CH₄ emissions reduction scenario by 2055, and lower than the objective of 0.2 °C avoidance
268 aimed for in the Pledge.

269 Above changes in 2046-2050 mean surface temperatures are, however, not
270 homogeneous over the globe (Figure 3). GMP (Figure 3a) avoids warming over a large part of
271 the globe, with exceptions over the North Atlantic, the Northwest Pacific, and the Southern
272 Ocean, as well as over Eastern Europe and the Mediterranean, which experience more warming
273 compared to the baseline scenario (CLE). Largest relative cooling is simulated to be over the
274 Arctic and the Northeast Pacific. The avoided warming over the Arctic and the North Atlantic
275 under the MTRF scenario (Figure 3d) is even greater, but this scenario also leads to more
276 pronounced warming over the Mediterranean, Western US, South America (Argentina), over
277 southern and Eastern Asia, and over the Antarctic. The figure also shows the areas where the
278 responses are within the 95% confidence interval based on student t test. Overall, the
279 simulated responses in surface temperatures are not significant in many regions, with the
280 exception of the Arctic region, where the response is consistently significant under all
281 scenarios. This is the case especially in MAP, where some large emitters like China are
282 signatories, although they have not signed in GMP, and in POL, which is the combination of
283 GMP and MAP, and MTRF, where all technically feasible reductions are considered. This
284 response agrees with literature, which shows that Arctic temperatures respond largest to

285 emission changes in Asia (Sand et al., 2015). This amplified response over the Arctic can be
 286 mainly attributed to feedback mechanisms rather than to concentration differences. As CH₄ is
 287 well-mixed, the concentration changes are rather spatially uniform (Figure S3), and CH₄
 288 amplifies Arctic processes that are already sensitive to perturbations outside the Arctic (Quinn
 289 et al., 2018; Christensen et al., 2019; Taylor et al., 2022).

290

291 **Figure 4.** Simulated surface temperature differences between GMP (a), MAP (b), POL (c), and
 292 MTRF (d) vs CLE averaged over 2046-2050. The dotted areas show responses within 95%
 293 confidence interval.

294 5 Discussion and Conclusions

295 Our results show that the GMP objective of achieving a reduction by 30% in 2030 global
 296 CH₄ emissions below the 2020 levels is not accomplished in the current GMP scenario or the
 297 POL (GMP+MAP) scenarios. This is, however, expected as 158 countries, accounting for roughly
 298 55% of the global anthropogenic emissions, have yet signed the Pledge.

299 Results show that the goal of avoiding 0.2 °C of warming by 2050 cannot be achieved
300 even under the most ambitious scenario. MTRF avoids a warming of 0.13 ± 0.12 °C; the current
301 commitments reflected in the GMP scenario only avoid 0.11 ± 0.11 °C by 2050. Results suggests
302 that a full participation in the Pledge can have the potential to achieve the Pledge's objectives
303 as taking the the large standard deviation into account. Results also show that the temperature
304 response in the GMP and MTRF scenarios are not proportional to the methane reductions.
305 Thus, even given the large uncertainties in the temperature response, it is challenging to
306 conclude whether or not there is really non-linearity in the response (Im et al., 2025a). The
307 GMP aims mitigation applied by ~2020, whereas our study considers emissions cuts starting a
308 few years later (2025), though this should only have a small impact. In addition, the GMP
309 derived the 0.2 °C goal based on the baseline emissions projections available in the GMA,
310 whereas our CLE scenario includes policies put into place since that time that led to lower
311 'baseline' emissions.

312 Results show that surface ozone (O_3) concentrations decrease slightly, from 24.5 ± 0.10
313 ppb in 2025 to 24.3 ± 0.06 ppb (by 1%) under GMP, while under the MTRF scenario global
314 surface O_3 concentrations can reduce by 23% to 18.9 ± 0.02 ppb in 2050. It should be noted in all
315 scenarios except for MTRF, the change in O_3 concentrations is due to changes in CH_4 emissions
316 only, while for MTRF, the estimated surface O_3 response is due to a combination of changes in
317 CH_4 and other SLCP emissions.

318 Our results are based on a single ESM with a small ensemble size. Ideally it should be
319 followed-up in a multi-model ensemble experiment, such as in the Methane Model

320 Intercomparison Project (MethaneMIP: England et al., 2025, <https://www.methanemip.org>).

321 We have used the GISS-E2.1-G interactive CH₄ simulations with 5 ensemble members in CMIP6

322 (Allen et al., 2021) to estimate the impact of the ensemble size on surface temperature

323 responses. We have compared the standard deviation in the 3 and 5 member ensembles,

324 respectively. In both subsets, the standard deviation in the 2046-2050 period under SSP1-2.6

325 and SSP2-4.5 compared to SSP3-7.0 (~0.21 °C and ~0.32 °C, respectively) remains much larger

326 than the ensemble mean (~-0.07 °C and ~-0.15 °C), which suggests that the ensemble size may

327 not be the governing factor of the large uncertainty in the temperature responses.

328 Previous studies have highlighted that the response of CH₄ concentrations to changes in

329 emissions is not necessarily linear as the chemistry is non-linear, and dependent on the

330 oxidative capacity of the atmosphere, also due to other species that impact OH (Im et al.,

331 2025a). For example, without halogens, models often overestimate methane lifetime, since

332 halogens contribute to an additional CH₄ sink (Saiz-Lopez & von Glasow, 2012; Sherwen et al.,

333 2016; Schmidt et al, 2016) and underestimate its near-term removal efficiency following

334 emission reductions (Hossaini et al., 2016) and can overestimate its concentrations and

335 radiative forcing. These imply that models need to be improved in their representation of

336 chemical composition and processes that influence chemical sinks of CH₄, and CH₄ emissions

337 from natural sources such as oceans, lakes, and permafrost should be better quantified.

338

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346

347 **Open Research**

348 The model output used to perform the analyses and create plots are provided in Zenodo:
349 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16755923> (Im et al., 2025b). The GISS-E2.1 model code used in
350 the present study, modelE2.1.2, is available under the GISS Model E Source Code Snapshots
351 webpage: <https://simplex.giss.nasa.gov/snapshots/modelE2.1.2.tgz> (NASA).

352

353 **Conflict of Interest Disclosure**

354 The authors declare there are no conflicts of interest for this manuscript.

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356

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